

Asta Ja and Asta Marga Coinciding for Managing the resources for Buddhist Economics Perspective. Designing Model Village Program**Shiva Adhikari**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18852446>**Review: 04/02/2026****Acceptance: 04/02/2026****Publication: 03/03/2026****Abstract:**

Management of resources becomes the major part of the function of government to design model village in each and every country in the world. Management is the strength of any project without which none of the bodies succeed to achieve the goal even if that might be performing by the government undertakings and other private entities. Then the program of the government now a day entails launching the program mutually designing to achieve the sustainable development goal given by the UN targeting to achieve within 2030. Even the development program always takes place for growth not merely making sustainability. But the sustainability concentrated on the program for peace in the human world. Peace depends upon the ground of human satisfaction with the products produced from the utilization of the Asta Ja resources managed by the trained hands of human resources learning the lesson of Asta Marga. With all the matters concerning the welfare of the community in the Model Village would be a means of happiness through the system followed by Buddhist Economics. With all the process present economics problem only be solve with the initiation of every government designing model village program globally. With the setting of model village maintenance of global peace providing the opportunity to generate a great source of income to be abundance for right livelihood.

Introduction,

People used to be saying picking the proverb from the ancestor that they say as you sow so you reap becoming the unique one to learn a lot from the six wording short sentence. It's because all are looking for noble personalities for the national development. Then again the big organization the UN (United Nation) also seeking some more effective tools to influence the government and people in the world. In the 2001 this organization announced the millennium development goal for overall development. In the same perspective on **25 Sept 2015** the UN again showed another face with Sustainable Development Goal announcement that should be achieved within 2030. The goal fixed in number 17 with the analytical socio-economic condition of the world and the agenda there are 169 guiding the goal to achieve so far.

With such mysterious path to go for sustainable process each and every government and the people in their capacity at first, has to be educated about the goal that has been announced by the UN. But how that may evaluate and achieved within the stipulated time, Once Prof. Jeffrey Sachs the architect of the goal, I had an opportunity

to meet and discuss about Sustainable Goal to that I argued it too more points how to make it functioning. After listening he became serious and asked how can we achieve the sustainable development. Then I said we have set everywhere a model village there the people will be trained with Asta Marga to make people well-disciplined to go for Utilizing Asta Ja resources. Then he became convinced to go through this way receiving my article published in Byabasthapan Journal. Therefore, I encouraged to go for the study on designing model village that through the way of Buddhist Economic Perspective. Therefore, all the concerned authorities must come to be designing model village to present economic harmony in the world.

Objective of the Study

Obviously, the objective of the study goes on careful management of the Asta Ja resources what mentioned earlier in this paper that may protect the environment making all happy and peaceful living in the Model Village. To make well managed the objective elaborating on different points are as:

- I. Ultimately the study aims to design the Model Village where the resources defined in the Asta Ja could be managed for the production of the product that may go on to satisfy human needs on an equal basis to maintain peace in the human world.
- II. Improve the economic development of the country and society through the way of human resource management giving all of them learn the lesson of Asta Marga that makes all well-disciplined to work on resource management.
- III. Providing the techniques how the resource could be managed in a perfect way that become rightly safe and productive to go through the process in the cycle of Identifying, Utilizing, and Conserving till to reach to receive the final product that may send in use selling in the market. Because conservation of the resources may protect the environment reducing global warming as well
- IV. Acclimate, the study with the goal of sustainable development and how that will have achieved in stipulated time.
- V. Recommending, managing the right livelihood in the Model Village community for achieving rapid economic growth working together to build a sustainable, prosperous, equitable, and just society by maintaining Sustainable Peace in the entire human world.

Methodology

The Buddhist Economics system, for the management of available resources needed to make equally benefited, avoiding all the difficulties in the economic world. Therefore, this study follows the matter that are available in the web pages and consulting Buddhist literature published in the books and magazines. Fundamentally the study is based on the books 'Small is beautiful' of E.F.Schumacher, 'Buddhist Economics' by Clair Brown Professor in the university California US, and the writings of Ven P.A.Payutta, Phabhanaviriyakhun (Phadet Bayya Jeevo), and more becoming the source to come to bring the document in this shape right now. Besides Buddhist Philosophical Books were thoroughly studied to prepare human resources on how to make actively working with their noble spirit.

Moreover, a structured questionnaire was also used to receive the opinion of the participants, on what most of the respondents responded in the internet to complete the study with full of productive results. Compiling all the

opinions of the respondents a brief recommendation has been given to the authorities to improve the economic character with the noble hands of human resources. All these sustainable development goals will be achieved in the model village community maintaining sustainable peace in the human world.

Research has been designed with the matter collected from the books on Buddhist Economics presented in the literature review. This study becomes a unique one to present a model of economics managing Asta ja (Eight Ja) resources with the lesson learning Asta marga (Eightfold Path) of Buddha to make all noble citizens who come to be controlling corruption of the socio-economic world. Buddhist Economics is the model that leads the society through the way of middle path making all aware of working together in the community. Community discipline would be of major concern to adopt the new economic harmony in the world could be right aim of the study.

The study then depends upon the following figuratively given the process as shown in the following model:

Research is generally based on descriptive modality deriving the opinion from the responses tabulating what are presented in the figurative model

Need of Resource Management

Management is the behavior of human resources that needs to be urgently prepared to provide the skill to go on utilizing the other resources. The fundamental description of the resources is given categorically into eight groups. Then the human resource falls into one group that deserves only the strength to manage the rest of all. Therefore, human resources if managed rightly every resource available in nature could be perfectly utilized to produce the products for human satisfaction.

Lesson of Buddha and social reform, learning Astanga Marga Eightfold Path

Buddha becoming the real leader who lead the society with well realization. It becomes the fact that if the problem realized rightly then only the way for solving the process could be realized. Therefore, the Asta Marga (Eightfold Path) becomes the right solution of the society that may purified every obstacle happened in the society. In fact, so, realization could be sought out through the eightfold path of Buddha. Just that comes first the 1. Right views, looking through the ways rightly directed. For that if the mind becomes able to find the fact about the viewers. In the same way the related part of seeing comes the next is 2. Right intention. This become very much practical what used to be looking through loosing the eyes how so it sees the matter. Looking should be done with right intention. If the things watched positively. The next step is the 3. Right speech that indicates speaking politely that may not be pinching the heart of the listeners. Speech generates the teaching to the disciples through what the right way of speaking should be produced. Then comes 4. Right action must be followed by the learning from the lesson of Buddha because the action must not be hurting the others and that should be rightly productive what the model village designing would be the result of right action.

Then the 5. Right Livelihood comes to make people living in the model village peacefully where every individual member of the community must be disciplined by learning the lesson of right views, right intention, right speech, right action to come to be in the place maintaining right livelihood. In the Buddha's time what seems he passed hard time in his life but he was not feeling any pain in his body. But he went on giving the example to change the mind of the people like even Angulimala his father was the Chaplain (minister) to the king of Kosala. Being from the high ranked family he became a murder even he used to wear the garland of the fingers cutting human beings. But the Buddha changed him into his disciple Vikshu. " In due cours Venerable Angulimala attained Arahantship. Referring to is memorable conversion by the Buddha" Narada-Buddha and His Teaching page 382. Learning the lesson of the Buddha Asta Marga to bring changes people even vandalism one like Angulimala..

The teaching of the next comes the 6. Right Effort means the effort of the person may not harm the people around him/her in the community. That also generating through the way of noble truth of the Buddha and Eightfold path so far. Then the 7. Right Mindfulness becomes the effective tools of the person who has been learning Buddhism. Mindfulness is the matter of diligently realized mindful to know the body guided by sensations and feelings. It's related to the activities of Body and sensation that may guide the people to be noble citizen or member in the community. 8. Right Concentration is the destiny of Buddhist teaching reaching to learn to this stage anyone feel full of joys self-concentrating and body with full realization. This stage has been leading by dhyana that generally called trance or recueillement –web page. Where all the sensual organs become very much silence to make all well-disciplined. .

Realization

Realization on the fact is the essence of Buddhist Philosophy. Because we all need to be realized who we are and what we doing? If not society suffers with the activities done by the people. So Siddharth Gautam left the palace and luxuries for the people because he realized the fact what should be done for the welfare of the society. Therefore, bringing any program from the capacity from the government that should come to be realizing the fact about the cases. To that effect everyone should know about how to make people happy. That has been realized by the king of Bhutan Jigme Sinngye Wangchuk who started the happiness program because he wanted to see all the citizen happy in his country. This program is based on Buddhist Economics. With the effectiveness of the program United Nations Organization also started to release the happiness index of the respected member countries. This program is the effect of realization of the cases. So that each and every country in the globe must come to be realized the particular cases of the society and adopt the appropriate program for the happiness of the people.

Identification and Management of Asta Ja (eight ja) resources

Management of the resources that starts describing what all are available in the community that's all come on the use for the benefits of the community people. So, the resources fundamentally grouped into Asta Ja (Eight Ja) that are described into eight categories are briefly introduced in the following points as: Name of the resources starts as if categorized starting into Nepali words they all would properly be naming eight Ja. Ja is the eight letter Ja from Nepali vernacular forms the name of the resources. Then Ja has been taken a source to describe the resources as: 1.Ja: Jal-water is the lifesaving resource that quenches thirst of the people, irrigates the land for cultivation, generates power in the project of hydroelectricity and so many benefits could be taken the people in the society utilizing water. Then 2. Ja: Jamin- land land is also the living place without which none of the species could be safe. In land human being built buildings for living, cultivate land for growing food, create garden for recreations and planting fruits for getting wonderful fruits and also land gives the herbal medicine to make people safe from the disease. 3. Ja: Jungle- forest becomes the right resources to make all the species actively living in the land. Forest also grows in the land but it has special character to make people happy generating income from the wood making different furniture's and also somehow forest used to build building and so on. 4.Ja:Jadibuti- Medicinal or Aromatic Herbs that generates tremendous medicinal products to cure the disease of the community people. Such medicinal plants are growing in the lap of Himalayas in Nepal. All such resources are self-growing but some go to pick them and sell in good pricing even in the international market. Medicinal herbs are the major resources that generates enough income to the people in Nepal. If people become rich, the country becomes rich itself what the late king who unified the country Prithvi Narayan Shah used to be saying if people become rich palace gets rich from their good work ' Praja Baliya Bhaya Durbar Baliyo Hunchha'. So, this resources must be utilized properly conserving them planting in some parts to generate income for the people and also government as well. If government came to realize the value of the medicinal herbs starting research in this field could be of the large amount of benefit could achieved. If so happen the products from the herbs essential oil and medicine could be sold in the international market that generates income instead sending youths in the overseas to sell their labor. 5.Ja:Jarajuri- plants, Nepal has various plants that value high in the foreign market. From the available plants in the land of Nepal produced food grains to feed people providing healthier food. Nepal has wonderful settings of land that grows different types of agricultural products what could be sold in the international market. If so all engaged in cultivating land scientifically none of the individual need to be looking job in the foreign labor market.

Instead Nepal can invite labor from the foreign countries for working in the farm as well. 6. Jalabayu (Climate) is the another types of resources that has been mentioned in the Asta Ja (Eightfold Path). Because Climate is the major part of resources that does not come to be in scene but all could be felt how pleasant is it. Climate is the major part that keeps significant role to promote all the resources in the nature. It lays greater "impacts the natural resource base, such as biodiversity by growing forest types, conserving wild animals, protecting water resources and soils and more. Ecological balance also could be maintained by the favorable climate that's available in Nepal. Different types of agricultural production could be done in such favorable climate. If people start working as per the climatic significance they become rightly rich in the country. The next is 7. Ja: Janawar –Animal what becoming tremendous source of income for the country. Animals use to be described in two types housekeeping and wild both are significant source of income for the people and the country so far. Some people participate for Hati polo-Elephant game in Chitwan internationally becoming right attraction of the people in the world. Also people use to come to see the rare types of animals visiting different parts that promotes tourism. With all people used to start poultry, cattle farming and so many activities that's all are the industries generating fertilizer in the farming field and income to the entrepreneur. And nation. .8. Ja: Janasakti –Manpower, human resource plays significant role for mobilizing the resources. Because human beings are the creator that bring heavy changes in the livelihood. Therefore, Asta marga (eightfold path) of the Buddha need to be taught them all to make well disciplined, none corrupt, honestly working for human welfare is the moto of the study.

Model Village Program

Government should proceed the program to design model village community that would be one of the best settlements in the community living indeed. Where all the requirement to satisfy each and every member of the community could be supplied easily. Human welfare, happiness, and sustainable peace could be, assured through Model Village Program. In the Model Village community, there must be a set program to teach the lesson, Asta Marga, to the community people giving them different types of production programs by mobilizing the resource. The effort during the study of Israeli technology has been used in the agriculture farm, becoming fruitful to produce quality product in desirable quantities to send to the market in different parts. Manamuri Agriculture Cooperative market is one in Gothatar managed by a women group of farmers becoming the model developed during the study could easily observing as an example in this regard. Then again the Muna Agricultural Market managed by Non-Residential Nepalese (NRN), and the more all over the country performing well in this regard should be the program of the government for national development that has been suggested to start in every part.

Resource management model designed herewith described in Asta Ja (Eight Ja) becomes quite an effective one to manage resources available in every part of the globe. Picking up one from Ast Ja human resource if prepared giving the lesson of Asta Marga to send them to manage the remaining 7 groups of resources would produce high-value products to use in the entire world. If human resources were prepared by providing the training they would be coming out with sharp knowledge and skill to mobilize the resources carefully. To make them so disciplined and noble human resources the lesson Asta Marga (Eightfold Path) should be given in the model village community regularly. With all this maintenance of sustainable peace in the world would be assured making all living in peace in the entire world. Therefore, a sincere suggestion to the government to make the program of Model Village in every part of the nation. If the model village designing happened in every part that would be a competitive part of development among the village would surely uplift the economy of the country.

Buddhist Economics is the economic system that creates every financial performance with Economics maintaining Good Governance. Because this economic system is geared toward the motive of good governance with the noble hand of the human resources that would be well trained by learning the lesson of Asta Marga. Following the combination, if actively gone through the ways working together new world economic harmony would be ascertained. The components could ostensibly be mentioned above are clearly shown in the table that is in the process given bellow as:

Functional Components	Processed	Achievement
Asta Ja (eight Ja)	Buddhist Economic System	Model Village Development
Asta Marga (Eightfold path)		
Eight Sustainable Goal		

In the table, functional components are shown in the initial column then the process starts to send the resources in the production function to achieve the goal that should be Model Village Community management would be the right conclusion and the recommendation of this study.

Management of resources if picked up here for the study what remains here again to go in the further notice for economic prosperity. It's because Asta Ja fundamental framework for production by utilizing the resources becomes so sharp means to promote the economy of a community, society, nation, and the human world. To prove this issue following quarry has been given to the respondents on what they prefer to go with the Buddhist Economics that becomes a most effective instrument to revive the economy derailed by different reasons in the globe:

Buddhist economics is one of the best approaches to solving global problems of poverty, inequality, cheating, threat, murder, and deprivation

No.	1-Much Sure	2-Sure	3-Neutral/relative,	4-Not sure	5- absolutely not
9	17.8%	37.5%	27.5%	14.9%	2.3%

Table 4.6. G-9:

The above table shows the Buddhist economics only becomes the major tool to solve the present economic problem in the world.

Asta Ja resources managing disciplined hand learning Astanga Marga

With all these how Asta Ja resource management goes on functioning for human welfare could be one model that shows the flow to reach the Model Village that becomes a peace center in the community. The model diagram is given here focusing on the Model Village that is based on the community used to be working, learning, and living happily in the Sangh that was the community formed in the time of the Buddha. Then Asta Ja (Eight Ja), resources all the time available to use for the benefit of the people. Since time immemorial human beings and the species

living on the globe utilizing the resources available and the skill to utilize to produce the products to satisfy their need.

In the diagram Asta Ja (Eight Ja), Asta Marga (Eightfold Path), Eight Sustainable goals side by side functioning through Buddhist Economics targeting to reach the Model Village program successfully. A brief on Sustainable Development Goal of the UN mentioned

Concentrating on the way of designing Model Village for overall development to revive the economy wrecked by the pandemic hit and the other war and social dispute in the countries and in between over the last year experienced bitterly in the world. War becomes a terrible example making it worst in some countries like Iraq, Afghanistan, and Libya in the name of establishing of democratic system devastating even for the infrastructure developed by the particular nations. Sustainable Development

Sustainable development goal of the UN has been a global package becoming the universal program since it has been announced on 25 Sept 2015 targeting to achieve within 2030 by United Nations Development Program (UNDP). In the announcement, there are 17 sustainable goals to be achieved successfully through the way activating the leading 169 agendas launched all over the world in its member countries. In this study, Asta ja

(Eight ja) resource management in a cycle with the learning, Asta Marga (Eightfold Path) of Buddha to make people able to handle all the resources perfectly. Like in the same way. Eight sustainable development goals have also taken in this study combining all the 17 goals from the Sustainable Development Program of the United Nations Organization (UNO) as in the following becoming related to design model village program globally. Thus the sustainable development program outlining here are eight in numbers as:

1. Clean Water and Sanitation for all (SDG 6)
2. Equitable quality education (SDG 4)
3. Full and productive employment / Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8)
4. Accessible to energy or Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)
5. Sustainable consumption and production pattern (SDG 12)
6. Protect eco system/life on Land (SDG 15)
7. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture/ Zero Hunger (SDG 2)
8. Reduce inequality and End of poverty in all its forms everywhere (SDG 10)

Buddhist Economics in practice

Management of the resources plays a significant role in the economic system valuing every component measuring in the money came to be used all units. So, the novelist Somerset Maugham given one of the instances of this issue said 'money is like a sixth sense, without which you cannot make complete use of the other five (K.P.Padmanabhan-Rural Credit, page 1, Published Intermediate Technology Publications Ltd, Southampton Row, London-1988). Hence, the management of economic programs takes a significant part of the society to keep all actively working in the field of production. Regarding the social matter, Buddhist Economy mentioned as its economics as if People Matter by E.F. Schumacher in his book Small is Beautiful seems quite a beautiful matter to people all around the world. The book published in 1975 enlightens all as the Buddha makes them aware to be happy enough in their lifetimes.

Schumacher mentions that 'Right Livelihood' is one of the requirements of the Buddha's Noble Eightfold Path' definitely becoming the base of economic development. Highlighting briefly the need of the time is Buddhist Economics Dr. Keshab Man Shakya describes the different applications in the countries mostly in Asia. First in Bhutan the then King Jigme Singhe Wangchuk proposed the Gross National Happiness (GNH) in 1972 becoming a major tool of the UN. Following the same concept, the UN start publishing the happiness index of the member countries in 2012. The argument over the concept is better than that of measuring the way given by IMF, Gross National Income, Gross National Products whatever used to be taken in practice GNH becoming a substantial part of the socio-economic behavior of UN.

Like, in the same way, the Sarvodaya (Sri Lanka Model) Buddhist Model of A. T. Ariyaratne, who was working as a school teacher started cooperative in March 1983 becoming a national economic system of the country as well. In the same way Sufficiency Economy in Thailand, King Bhumibol Adulyadej started to promote the standard of living of the people which became another model of Buddhist Economics. Then again in India State Socialism (Ambedkar Model) used to be launched according to the Buddhist Economics Model and also came

into practice managing reservation to the people in the lower strata to uplift them on a general equitable basis that still becoming a popular system in India.

In the same way, Japan has adopted Soka Gakkai (Value Creating Society) which becomes instrumental to revive the devastated economy due to the deadly bombarding in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. The Japanese people were the follower of the Buddha learning the lesson of Asta Marga and they became so noble in character didn't even think about retaliation against the US. They started revenge by working hard to build the nation to make beautiful starting the development of the countries. Buddhist Economics could make the nation a developed country becoming a model system in the world also mentioned in the writing of Dr. Shakya in his article published in CNAS-HiPeC Discussion Series 2013. Not only mentioned in this section other countries in Asia like China, Taiwan, Mongolia, and others coming to adopt the Buddhist Economics System gradually.

Buddhist Economist P.A. Payutta a leading monk-scholar in his book mentioned 'a middle way for the market place (1994) criticized the tendency of modern economics to examine' economic values how that exist in the socio-economic development of a nation. Prof. Clair Brown Published a book on Buddhist Economics (an enlightened approach to dismal science) in 2017 is another source to know the need for a new economic model on the way to recover the devastating economy from different wars and disasters. Therefore, this study is concerned about the Management of Asta Ja Resources for Sustainable Development Designing Model Village in Buddhist Economic perspective becoming a need of the time to bring into practice for human welfare.

Resource Management Cycle

Consequently, before to go on utilizing the resources, human part must be prepared by giving the lesson of Asta Marga that makes all perfect to work with a noble spirit. Then only resources would be perfectly utilized through the way in the cyclical process so as identification of the resources to find what the matter that how to bring changes into the product that may value in use for the satisfaction of the society. The same then if utilized or processed in action that will produce the right product, and after utilization the resources indigenously receiving must be conserved that may protect the natural environment by providing the opportunity to use the same for the future generation. Then the considerable part of the cycle goes in the following figure:

The model given in the figure becomes the crux of the study and runs from the identification, utilization, and conservation of the resources that may keep the environment in order to reduce global warming. Jeffrey Sachs in this context argues that the richest countries in the world like America concentrate on the maximization of income and profits from investment and business promotion neglecting the social and environmental sectors what becoming he says the wrong economic behavior neglecting the social and environmental sector to achieve sustainable goal. If the US neglects both the socio-environmental part in the society that may resulting worst scenario generating global warming what becomes very dangerous to the human world. Therefore, how the resources send in processing would be tested in the responses of the participants as in the following tabulation that valuing the process virtually in the tabular and diagrammatic forms. Eight Fold paths of Buddhism and Asta Ja approach (mobilizing eight major resources in sustainable manner) of development can be linked in the process of resource use.

Respondents are just given their opinion that has been ranking in the table here the same result also depicted in the diagram that can be seen as:

No.	1-Much Sure	2-Sure	3-Neutral/relative,	4-Not sure	5- absolutely not
2	19.3%	48.4%	20.5%	10.4%	1%

With the responses of participants, the aim to design some new economic system could be the best way to manage the resources confidently given here the recommendation. Whatever the concept floating over the respondents they prefer to have a result in designing the model village community based on Buddhist Economics. With all these major arguments confidence onward raised to manage the resources with proper care that may produce the right result for the benefit of the community stratified into the different model villages as to similar management of the Buddha in Sangh. Detail of the program given in the study may use to be translated into practice to bring wonderful changes to make all happy enjoying desirable peace in the human world.

Recommendation.

Currently the economy of Nepal heavily depends upon remittance received from the youth labor force in the Gulf countries, and some are working in Malaysia, Israel, different European countries, Australia, America, Canada, and abroad. Observing all these, governments must be careful to stop the youth force from providing employment opportunities creating different productive projects. The productive sectors might be agriculture, medicinal and aromatic herbs, livestock, fisheries, poultries, and different small and cottage industries promoting the indigenous profession in the country. If such the different sectors were carefully mobilized would become a great source of income from the use of resources to the nation-making self-reliant society. For the extension of the sectors mentioned here should be based on the research for identification, utilization, and conservation carefully so that the environment could be managed properly. All these recommendations to launch a program based on Buddhist Economics are given in the following points:

Model Village Program

Government should proceed with the model village community that would be one of the best settlements where every requirement would be fulfilled making people satisfied. Human welfare, happiness, and sustainable peace

could be, assured through Model Village Program. In the Model Village community, there must be a set program to teach the lesson, Asta Marga, to the community people to set different types of production programs by mobilizing the resource. The effort during the study of Israeli technology has been used in the agriculture farm, becoming fruitful to produce product in desirable quantities that may send all in the local and international market starting community collection center in different parts. Manamuri Agriculture Cooperative market is one in Gothatar managed by a women group of farmers becoming the model developed during the study could easily observing as an example in this regard. Then again the Muna Agricultural Market managed by Non-Residential Nepalese (NRN), and the more all over the country performing well in this regard should be the program of the government for national development that has been suggested. Definitely model village has been sought out the replication of Sangha where the disciples of Buddha used to be living peacefully the same structure has been proposed in the model village all the community members enjoying right livelihood.

Proper Utilization of the Resources

Major part of human resources is to manage the resources remaining the other bringing all change to make worth utilizing in the society. If so well managed the resources human world be living peacefully having everything desirable at hand. Therefore, government and the concerned authorities should go to change society through the way of management of resources supplementing them all processed in the industries and so other with a creative sense of energetic human force. Therefore, the government of particular countries must manage the resources by starting industries based on renewable processing through the Buddhist Economic perspective.

Buddhism and Modern Capitalist Economics

Buddhism is about wisdom and how that goes on creating a lovely habit to behave the people in the community. This indicates the one in the society to become wise enough is the Buddha. Wisdom then generates a lot of benefits to the community people where no one feels harm, none would be deceived and discriminated against from the behavior of the people living in the community. Buddhist philosophy is the core behavioral patterns of human beings that mention well enough how to make all happy and maintain peace in the human world. In the same way, the Buddhist Economics system is the system of management of Asta Ja resources that gives ways and techniques to produce the product with the hands of skillful people learning the lesson Asta Marga what makes all honest, well-disciplined whatever they do becomes very much useful to keep people always satisfied equally.

Concerning the suffering of human beings, Clair Brown seems so worried about the 'global inequality can be hard to fathom'. She mentioned the instances of her traveling 'to the slums of Mumbai or rural villages in Ethiopia and seen hungry, stunned children living in the dark, crowded rooms without running water or a pace of poop' (Clair Brown-Buddhist Economics, page 86) all about what she experienced painfully the same happened to the Buddha while he was traveling around the palace escorted by his soldiers. Therefore, the Buddhist Economic system is the system of human welfare, what used to be produced from the effort of human beings that all go equally to the hands of each individual to satisfy all at once.

Prof. Clair Brown mentions 'Global wealth is concentrated in the hands of a small group of billionaires and their wealth has been growing rapidly' (ibid), becoming the concern of the wise scholars who are very much aware to equalize the outcome of the production from the resource used. If not managed the resources that are mentioned in the Asta Ja with the capacity of human beings to learn the lesson of Asta Marga of Buddha economy would be

ruined creating a chaotic situation in society. Therefore, the Capitalist Economy in the name of the modern economy or neo-liberalized economic system focuses to receive the maximum return of the investment and maximization of the profits in the industries merely benefits the few rich becoming a great disastrous situation making the majority of the people in poverty.

Conclusion

Desiring to bring changes into the society erasing all the pain used to be born in the community through the way of the Buddhist Model of human settlement in the Model Village definitely becoming a significant part of the study. Buddhist Economics defined by E.F. Schumacher given the concept of widening the way forward concentrating to launch the program to use renewable energy obviously would be a great step to manage the environment becoming the need of the time today.

The study on Buddhist Economics briefly recommends to the government here given to make systematic economic reform for national development. Going through the study the document government can design a program how to identify the natural resources to send all for production and ultimately receive the quality product that may greatly benefit to the society generating income by selling them in the national and international market instead sending the labor to the overseas countries.

References

1. E.F. Schumacher – Small is Beautiful –Economics as if People Matter, 1973
2. Clair Brown Ph.D. Professor California University US –Buddhist Economics –Bloomsbury Press, 2017
3. Poudel, D.D. 2008. Management of eight ‘Ja’ for economic development of Nepal, Journal of Comparative International Management, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 15-27.
4. Poudel, D.D. 2010a. A strategic framework for environmental and sustainable development in Nepal, International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development, [Forthcoming]
5. Poudel, D.D. 2010b. The Asta-Ja Environmental and Natural Resources Policy Framework (Asta-Ja ENRF) for Sustainable Development in Nepal, Journal of Comparative International Management, [Forthcoming].
6. Jeffrey Sachs - Professor California University US The End of Poverty, Penguin Publication in 2005
7. Artha Ratna Tuladhar –Avlokitesvar Karunamaya, Rato Matsyendranath in 2019
8. Yuval Noa Harari – Sapiens, 2014, Homo Dues -2017, Vintage, and 21st Lesson for 21st Century, Jonthan Cape London, 2018
9. Thomas Piketty – Capital in the Twenty First Century-The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2017
10. Adam Smith – Wealth of Nation –Bantam Classic, 2003
11. Narada – Buddha and His Teaching-Jaico Publishing House Ahamadabad-2020
12. CNAS-HiPeC Discussion Series – Implementatin of Buddhist Economic Virtues in National Development – Keshab Man Shakya, Shanker L. Chaudhary, and Triratna Manandhar -2013
13. National Review of Sustainable Development Goals – National Planning Commission Singhadurbar -2013
14. Wikipedia.Org/wiki/Buddhism
15. Economic Survey, Government of Nepal
16. Budget Speech of Fiscal Year, Government of Nepal